

Studies in Aeration. I. Determination of Henry's Law Constants and Adsorption Isotherm Parameters at Air-Water Interfaces for Hydrophobic Chlorinated Compounds from Solvent Sublation Experiments

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Manuscript received 4 December 1984, accepted 8 June 1985

Experimental results on solvent sublation of hydrophobic refractory chlorinated compounds of low aqueous solubility are used to determine the values of the coefficient α which control the extent of mass transfer across the air-water interface of the rising air bubbles in a solvent sublation column. For the various compounds studied the trend in α values suggests that larger the value of α the more hydrophobic the compound is and the more easily it is removed by solvent sublation. Mineral oil was found to be an extremely good organic 'solvent' (here 'solvent' refers to an immiscible organic liquid floating on top of the aqueous layer) for solvent sublation. The value of the adsorption parameter κ was observed to be extremely dependent on the rather imprecise value of V_o , the adsorption energy for these hydrophobic compounds at air-water interfaces.

SOLVENT sublation, a surface chemical technique first introduced by Felix Sebba¹ has proved to be capable of removing volatile surface active compounds from water. Mathematical models have been proposed and tested against experimental results on chlorinated hydrocarbons²⁻⁵, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons⁶, nitrophenols and dye-surfactant complex^{4,5} and phthalate esters⁷. However, very little information is available on the feasibility of the technique on a pilot-plant scale⁸. In solvent sublation hydrophobic compounds of low aqueous solubility are carried on the air-water interface and/or in the interior of the air bubbles rising through the aqueous column and are deposited in the mineral oil layer floated on top of the aqueous layer. In this report we use some of our results on chlorinated hydrocarbons to obtain experimental estimates of Henry's law constants and adsorption isotherm parameters which control the mass transfer of these materials across the air-water interface.

Theory :

Let us visualise the scenario of air bubbles rising through a homogeneous volume V_L of aqueous solution (Fig. 1) topped with an immiscible organic layer. If we consider mass transfer across the air-water interface of the rising bubbles we can write equation (1) for overall mass balance for a solute in a solvent sublation column.

$$\frac{dm_o}{dt} = \kappa_{oL} a V_L [C_L - C_L^*] \quad (1)$$

where, m_o = number of moles of material in/on the surface of the rising bubbles, κ_{oL} = overall liquid

Fig. 1. Schematic of solvent sublation process.

phase mass transfer coefficient (cm s^{-1}), a = interfacial area per unit volume of the liquid ($\text{cm}^2 \text{cm}^{-3}$), C_L = concentration in the bulk liquid phase (mol cm^{-3}), C_L^* = liquid concentration of the material in equilibrium with the gas phase, and Γ = concentration (mol cm^{-3}).

In writing the above mass balance it has to be pointed out that in solvent sublation material can enter the air phase by volatilisation and can also be adsorbed at the air-water interface. The value of

m_o is given by

$$m_o = V_o C_o + a V_z \Gamma \quad (2)$$

where, H = Henry's law constant for the material (dimensionless), V_z = overall volume of the liquid phase (cm^3), V_o = overall volume of the gas phase (cm^3), C_o = vapor phase concentration of the material (mol cm^{-3}), Γ = concentration of the material in the adsorbed phase (mol cm^{-3}).

Henry's constant, H is given by equation (3).

$$H = \frac{[\text{Vapor pressure, mm Hg}] [\text{Molecular weight}]}{(6.24 \text{ E4}) (\text{Temperature, K}) (\text{Aqueous solubility, g cm}^{-3})} \quad (3)$$

The vapor phase concentration C_g is then given by

$$C_g = H C_z^* \quad (4)$$

The adsorbed phase concentration Γ is assumed to be controlled by a Langmuir adsorption isotherm for monolayer adsorption; this being given by

$$\Gamma = \frac{\Gamma_{max} C_z^*}{C_{1/2} + C_z^*} \quad (5)$$

where, the constants Γ_{max} and $C_{1/2}$ are related to molecular parameters as reported earlier by us⁵

$$\Gamma_{max} = A_m^{-1}; C_{1/2} = \frac{\exp(\beta V_o)}{\nu_m} \quad (6)$$

where, A_m and ν_m are the molar areas and volumes, respectively of the adsorbed solute, β is the Boltzmann factor ($1/kT$) and V_o is the adsorption energy. We noted earlier^{4,5} that $C_{1/2} \gg C_z^*$ and therefore we can linearise the equation⁵, i.e. we are working in the linear range of the adsorption isotherm. This gives

$$\Gamma = \frac{\Gamma_{max} C_z^*}{C_{1/2}} = \kappa C_z^* \quad (7)$$

where, $\kappa = \Gamma_{max}/C_{1/2}$.

Using equations (4) and (7) in (2) and differentiating with respect to t

$$\frac{dm_o}{dt} = [V_o H + V_z a \kappa] \frac{dC_z^*}{dt} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{But } \frac{V_o}{V_z} = \frac{a V_b}{A_b} = \frac{ar}{3}$$

where, r is the average bubble radius.

Equating (1) and (8) and rearranging we get

$$\frac{dC_z^*}{dt} = [C_z - C_z^*] \frac{\kappa O_z}{\frac{r}{3} H + \kappa} \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) can be integrated using the initial condition that $C_z^* = 0$ at $t = 0$. We also use another assumption which we made use of in our earlier models³⁻⁶, viz. that during the time the bubble transits the slab (i.e. for $\tau = V_g/Q_o$, where, V_g is the volume of air and Q_o is the air flow rate), C_z does

not change considerably. This then yields

$$\frac{C_z^*}{C_z} = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{-\kappa O_z}{\frac{r}{3} H + \kappa} \left(\frac{V_o}{Q_o} \right) \left(\frac{t}{\tau} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

If we now consider the overall mass transfer coefficients as average values for the entire system, then the mass transfer rate of the material across the oil-water interface may be satisfactorily predicted as

$$N = Q_o \frac{m_o}{V_o} (t = \tau) \quad (11)$$

$$N = Q_o \left[H = \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right] C_z \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-\kappa O_z V_o}{\left\{ \frac{r}{3} H + \kappa \right\} Q_o} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

Experimental

The column was made of pyrex glass tubing (116 cm x 5.2 cm dia) with a fine fritted glass disc. Three stopcocks were arranged at 1, 54 and 110 cm from the bottom to allow liquid to be collected at various heights in the column. The temperature of the solutions were monitored by a thermometer inserted through the large rubber stopper sealing the top of the column. A piece of glass tubing was inserted through the same stopper and connected to a soap film flowmeter. The flow of house compressed air was controlled by a micrometer needle valve and passed through humidifier and a 15 cm glass drying tube packed with glass wool to remove dust, water droplets or oils before reaching the fritted disc. Flow rates were measured with a soap film flowmeter and a stopwatch. The experiments were timed with an electric timer. Experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Sublation apparatus. 1. Air needle valve, 2. Glass wool column, 3. Fritted glass disc, 4. Outlet port, 5. Sampling tap, 6. Thermometer, 7. Vent, 8. Soap film flowmeter, 9. Controlled temperature bath, 10. Wrapped tygon tubing.

1000 mg dm⁻³ solutions of *o*-dichlorobenzene, *p*-dichlorobenzene (both Eastman), polychlorinated biphenyl (Monsanto Aroclor 1254), lindane and endrin (Polyscience) were prepared in pesticide grade hexane (Fisher). To prepare aqueous solutions of these compounds known volumes (20-40 cm³) of hexane solutions were floated on 2 dm³ of distilled water and the solution kept stirred by aeration till all the hexane evaporated. These solutions were then calibrated against standard hexane solutions, after extracting the solutes into hexane. Solutions of required strength were prepared by dilution of these stock solutions.

The concentrations of these chlorinated organics were measured using a F and M 700 Laboratory gas chromatograph equipped with a Tracor Nickel-63 high temperature electron capture detector and a Tracor solid state electrometer. Purified nitrogen was the carrier gas; it was passed through a Matheson XF-100 gas chromatography scrubber to remove oxygen and water. A 5 foot silanized glass column packed with 4% SE-30 and 6% SP-2401 on 100/120 mesh Supelcoport was used. Peaks were recorded on a Honeywell Elektronik 15 recorder. Hamilton 701N series 10 μl syringes were used for injection through a Supelco Gray disc septum into the gas chromatograph.

The column was first rinsed with deionised water, filled with 2.2 dm³ of deionised water and the flow rate adjusted to the desired value. The water was then drained off and then the column was filled with the experimental solution. On top of this was added about 30-80 cm³ of octan-2-ol (in the case of dichlorobenzenes and PCBs) or 50 cm³ of mineral oil (in the case of lindane and endrin). The timer was started after filling the column. At the prescribed intervals samples of approximately 10 cm³ volume were removed from the middle tap into a 20 cm³ glass bottle. 2 cm³ hexane was added to the aqueous layer and the solution was well shaken to ensure complete extraction of the solute into the hexane layer. The bottle was covered with aluminum foil and well stoppered until analysis. The air flow rate through the column was checked after each sampling. After the experiment was over, the organic liquid was pipetted off and the solution drained from the bottom. The column was filled with 2.2 dm³ deionised water and aerated overnight. The column was then scrubbed withalconox solution and repeatedly washed with water so that no trace of octanol or paraffin oil was present.

Results and Discussion

In order to analyse our results on the batch column, we write the following mass balance equation for the bulk liquid phase concentration

$$-V_L \frac{dC_L}{dt} = N \quad (13)$$

Using equation (12) in (13) and integrating it using the initial condition C_L (at $t=0$) = C_L^0 we

obtain

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_L}{C_L^0} \right) = -\frac{Q_g}{V_L} \left[H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right] \left[1 - \exp \left\{ \frac{-\kappa_{OL} V_o}{\left(\frac{rH}{3} + \kappa \right) Q_g} \right\} \right] t \quad (14)$$

We have noted⁹ in a detailed theoretical analysis of solvent sublation that in the tall columns we used for solvent sublation, effective mass transfer is possible only for bubbles in the range of radii 0.01-0.04 cm and that large bubbles move too fast through the column. The effectiveness of very small bubbles (preferably of radii 0.01-0.04 cm) and the consequent success of solvent sublation depends on long contact times for the bubbles and large interfacial area/volume ratio. Our experimental conditions were, therefore, such that $\frac{\kappa_{OL}}{(rH + \kappa)} \cdot \frac{V_o}{Q_g} \gg 1$. This is a con-

dition similar to the one used by Mackay *et al.*¹⁰ to determine Henry's law constants for hydrophobic pollutants. An identical treatment for simple aeration was later used by Matter-Muller *et al.*¹¹. Later in this paper we will show how this condition is satisfied in our experiments. Under these conditions equation (14) reduces to

$$\ln \frac{C_L}{C_L^0} = -\frac{Q_g}{V_L} \left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right) t \quad (15)$$

Hence, from the slope of the plot of $\ln C_L/C_L^0$ vs t we can obtain estimates of $\left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right)$. Notice that experimental values of $\left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right)$ can at best give a good estimate of κ since H can be accurately known from simple aeration experiments (*i.e.* without any mineral oil on top of the aqueous layer)¹⁰. Our theoretical estimates of κ are fraught with uncertainties because of its exponential dependence on V_o through $C_{1/2}$ (equations 6 and 7); the value of V_o we noted earlier^{5,8} is quite an uncertain parameter, sometimes even 35% in error. We, therefore, choose to report the combined value $\left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right)$ for the chlorinated compounds. These values are reported in Table 1.

We note that fairly consistent values of $\left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right)$ are obtained for specific compounds. The small variations within a set of experiments are probably due to slight fluctuation in air flow rate at the start of the experiment and variations in bubble sizes inside the column. However, we do note that compounds which are highly hydrophobic, of very low aqueous solubility and considerably small values of $C_{1/2}$ (*e.g.* Aroclor 1254 and Endrin) have high values of $\left(H + \frac{3}{r} \kappa \right)$ and they tend to be removed faster from aqueous solution.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF OPERATING PARAMETERS AND $(H + \frac{3}{r}\kappa) = \alpha$ FOR VARIOUS CHLORINATED COMPOUNDS

Batch volume = 2.2 dm³.

Compd. sublated	Organic solvent used	Slope* s ⁻¹	Average air flow rate cm ³ s ⁻¹	$(H + \frac{3}{r}\kappa) = \alpha$ (dimensionless)	α (mean)
o-Dichlorobenzene	n-Octanol	1.34 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.5	0.196	0.182
		1.15 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.5	0.168	
p-Dichlorobenzene	n-Octanol	2.07 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.7	0.123	0.148
		1.17 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.5	0.172	
Aroclor 1254	Mineral oil	9.63 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.7	0.785	0.785
Lindane	Mineral oil	5.56 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.0	0.122	0.107
		8.33 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.0	0.092	
Endrin	Mineral oil	1.65 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.8	0.454	0.489
		3.85 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.0	0.424	

* Slope of the plot of $-\ln(C/C_0)$ vs time, C is the experimentally determined concentration.

 TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL ESTIMATES OF ADSORPTION ISOTHERM PARAMETER (κ)

Compd.	H (dimensionless)	Γ_{max} mol cm ⁻³ × 10 ⁻¹⁰	$C_{1/2}$ (mol cm ⁻³)	κ (theory) cm	κ (experimental) cm
o-Dichlorobenzene	0.071 ^a	3.6	7.5 × 10 ⁻⁷	4.8 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.0 × 10 ⁻⁴
p-Dichlorobenzene	0.047 ^a	3.6	7.61 × 10 ⁻⁷	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴
Aroclor 1254	0.112 ^b	2.1	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	2.1 × 10 ⁻³	4.0 × 10 ⁻³
Lindane	1.3 × 10 ⁻⁴ ^a	3.3	1.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	2.5 × 10 ⁻³	7.1 × 10 ⁻⁴
Endrin	2.78 × 10 ⁻⁴ ^b	2.3	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁶	2.1 × 10 ⁻³	2.9 × 10 ⁻³

^a Ref. 12. ^b Ref. 5.

We also wish to point out that by suitably adjusting the value of V_0/Q_0 and thereby making

$\frac{\kappa_{O_2} V_0}{(H + \frac{3}{r}\kappa) Q_0} \ll 1$, we can determine $\kappa_{O_2} a$ values from

the slope of the plot of $\ln C_L/C_L^0$ vs t , i.e. for very small contact time and the exit gas far from saturation,

$$\ln \frac{C_L}{C_L^0} = -\frac{V_0}{V_L} \kappa_{O_2} a \left[\frac{H + \frac{3}{r}\kappa}{\frac{rH}{3} + \kappa} \right] t = -(\kappa_{O_2} a) t \quad (16)$$

For compound of low Henry's constants (as in our case) this condition is difficult to satisfy experimentally. This point has been adequately described by Munz and Roberts¹³. An indirect method of relating the mass transfer coefficient of stripping of a particular compound to the mass transfer coefficient for absorption of oxygen into water is, therefore, suggested to determine $(\kappa_{O_2} a)^{13}$. We did not attempt this in the present case. On the other hand, a rough theoretical calculation we did earlier^{5,6} showed that the range of κ_{O_2} values should be 1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-2} cm s⁻¹ for most of these hydrophobic compounds. For a bubble of radius 0.02 cm, the residence time in our column is approximately 25 s, i.e. $\tau = \frac{V_0}{Q_0} \approx 25$. These values in conjunction with the value of α show that the condition

$\frac{\kappa_{O_2} Q_0}{rH + \kappa} \gg 1$ is always satisfied in our experi-

ments. This condition, therefore, excludes the determination of κ_{O_2} from our experimental results.

From the values of α obtained as above one can obtain experimental estimates of κ , the adsorption isotherm constant. This was accomplished by first estimating the average bubble radii in the column using photographs of the column in operation (details of the method are available in our earlier publications^{5,6}). The average bubble radius thus estimated at air flow rates between 1.0 and 4.0 cm³ s⁻¹ was 0.02 cm. Henry's constants H were obtained from the reported results^{5,12}. The theoretical values of Γ_{max} and $C_{1/2}$ were also obtained from the reported results⁶. The results thus obtained are shown in Table 2.

It is evident from Table 2 that the experimental and theoretical estimates of κ vary considerably for the last three compounds. We attribute this to the imprecise knowledge of V_0 (the adsorption energy at air/water interface) for these compounds. We noted earlier⁵ from our theoretical treatment of the statistical mechanics of adsorption at air/water interfaces that $C_{1/2}$ shows an exponential dependence on V_0 and, therefore any slight error in estimation of V_0 will show up as a greatly magnified

error in $C_{1/2}$. This is evident from equation (6) which gives

$$\kappa = \frac{\nu_m}{A_m} \exp(-\beta V_o) \quad (17)$$

The most of the discrepancy between κ (theory) and κ (experimental) can be traced to the uncertainty in the knowledge of V_o . Allowing for this uncertainty, the discrepancy between the experimental and theoretical estimates of κ seems reasonable.

In conclusion, we wish to point out that as in the case of simple aeration, we can determine the Henry's constant, the adsorption isotherm parameters (or more realistically a combination of the two) and mass transfer coefficient in solvent sublation experiments by suitably adjusting the operating parameters.

We also noted that mineral oil was the best solvent possible, both from an economic point of view as well as from a health perspective (because of its immiscibility with water). Moreover, it also avoids the problems of odour which we observed was a persistent problem with octanol.

Conclusion :

From the information given in this paper we can draw the following conclusions.

(i) Solvent sublation is quite effective in removing hydrophobic refractory compounds of low solubility in water which are otherwise not easily removable by simple bubble aeration. This is a reinforcement of our earlier observation on polynuclear aromatics⁶.

(ii) The ease of solvent sublation is directly related to the magnitude of κ , i.e. $(H + \frac{3}{r}\kappa)$; the larger its value is, the better the removal. A systematic investigation of other compounds with a view to determining this parameter would go a long way in assessing the feasibility of solvent sublation as a viable industrial wastewater treatment process.

(iii) From health perspectives as well as from an economic point of view mineral oil seems to be an excellent organic 'solvent' for solvent sublation experiments.

(iv) One other important point we wish to bring to notice is the fact that solvent sublation is more

useful than aeration because (a) by solvent sublation we can possibly control the undesirable release of materials into the atmosphere and (b) materials which are surface-adsorbed on the air-water interface (which cannot be removed by simple aeration) can also be removed by solvent sublation.

(v) The discrepancies between the experimental and theoretical values of κ can be reconciled by a precise knowledge of the adsorption energy, V_o . Nevertheless, for hydrophobic compounds with unfavorable Henry's constant, we can conclude that larger the κ value (larger the adsorption energy from equation 17) the more effective solvent sublation would be in removing them aqueous solutions *via* adsorption at air-water interfaces.

(vi) Further experiments on oxygen reaeration are necessary to determine the mass transfer coefficients in solvent sublation columns.

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